

SPECIAL CHARACTERIZATIONS OF RECTANGLES IN CONNECTION WITH TRIMORPHIC NUMBERS

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ABSTRACT. This paper consists of two sections A and B. Section A exhibits rectangles, where, in each rectangle, the area added with its semi-perimeter is a Trimorphic number. Section B presents rectangles, where, in each rectangle, the area minus its semi-perimeter is a Trimorphic number.

1. INTRODUCTION

In [1-16], the diophantine problems relate geometrical representations with special numbers, namely, Armstrong numbers, Sphenic numbers, Harshad numbers, etc. The above results motivated us for obtaining rectangles with special characterizations in connection with Trimorphic numbers.

It seems that the above problems has not been considered earlier.

2. METHOD OF ANALYSIS:

Let R be a rectangle with dimensions x and y . Let A and S be represents the Area and Semi-perimeter of R.

2.1. Section-A: $A+S = \text{Trimorphic number with digits 2, 3, 4, 5}$

. The problem under consideration is mathematically equivalent to solving the binary quadratic diophantine equation represented by

$$xy + (x + y) = \alpha \quad (\text{A-1})$$

where α is a Trimorphic number in turn.

Rewrite (A-1) as

$$x = \frac{\alpha - y}{y + 1} \quad (\text{A-2})$$

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Given α , it is possible to find x in integers for suitable y in integers. The following Table:1 exhibits the Trimorphic number with their corresponding rectangles satisfying (A-1):

Table 1: $\mathbf{A} + \mathbf{S} = \alpha$

α	R(x,y)	Observation	
		Primitive rect-angles	Non-Primitive rectangles
25	(1, 12), (12, 1)	2	—
49	(1, 24), (4, 9), (9, 4), (24, 1)	4	—
51	(1, 25), (3, 12), (12, 3), (25, 1)	2	2
75	(1, 37), (3, 18), (18, 3), (37, 1)	2	2
76	(6, 10), (10, 6)	—	2
99	(1, 49), (3, 24), (4, 19), (19, 4), (24, 3), (49, 1)	4	2
125	(1, 62), (2, 41), (5, 20), (6, 17), (8, 13), (13, 8), (17, 6), (20, 5), (41, 2), (62, 1)	8	2
249	(1, 124), (4, 49), (9, 24), (24, 9), (49, 4), (124, 1)	4	2
999	(1, 499), (3, 249), (4, 199), (7, 124), (9, 99), (19, 49), (24, 39), (39, 24), (49, 19), (99, 9), (124, 7), (199, 4), (249, 3), (499, 1)	8	6
1249	(1, 624), (4, 249), (9, 124), (24, 49), (49, 24), (124, 9), (249, 4), (624, 1)	8	—
3751	(1, 1875), (3, 937), (6, 535), (7, 468), (13, 267), (27, 133), (55, 66), (66, 55), (133, 27), (267, 13), (468, 7), (535, 6), (937, 3), (1875, 1)	12	2
4375	(1, 2187), (3, 1093), (7, 546), (546, 7), (1093, 3), (2187, 1)	4	2
4999	(1, 2499), (3, 1249), (4, 999), (7, 624), (9, 499), (19, 249), (24, 199), (39, 124), (49, 99), (99, 49), (124, 39), (199, 24), (249, 19), (499, 9), (624, 7), (999, 4), (1249, 3), (2499, 1)	18	—
5001	(1, 2500), (40, 121), (60, 81), (81, 60), (121, 40), (2500, 1)	4	2
9999	(1, 4999), (3, 2499), (4, 1999), (7, 1249), (9, 999), (15, 624),	12	10

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Table 1 – *Continued from previous page*

α	R(x,y)	Observation	
		Primitive rect-angles	Non-Primitive rectangles
	(19, 499), (24, 399), (39, 249), (49, 199), (79, 124), (124, 79), (199, 49), (249, 39), (399, 24), (499, 19), (624, 15), (999, 9), (1249, 7), (1999, 4), (2499, 3), (4999, 1)		
18751	(1, 9375), (3, 4687), (7, 2343), (15, 1171), (31, 585), (63, 292), (292, 63), (585, 31), (1171, 15), (2343, 7), (4687, 3), (9375, 1)	12	–
31249	(1, 15624), (4, 6249), (9, 3124), (24, 1249), (49, 624), (124, 249), (249, 124), (624, 49), (1249, 24), (3124, 9), (6249, 4), (15624, 1)	12	–
49999	(1, 24999), (3, 12499), (4, 9999), (7, 6249), (9, 4999), (15, 3124), (19, 2499), (24, 1999), (39, 1249), (49, 999), (79, 624), (99, 499), (124, 399), (199, 249), (249, 199), (399, 124), (499, 99), (624, 79), (999, 49), (1249, 39), (1999, 24), (2499, 19), (3124, 15), (4999, 9), (6249, 7), (9999, 4), (12499, 3), (24999, 1)	28	–
50001	(1, 25000), (22, 2173), (45, 1086), (1086, 45), (2173, 22), (25000, 1)	4	2

2.2. Section-B: A-S = Trimorphic number with digits 2, 3, 4, 5

. The problem under consideration is mathematically equivalent to solving the binary quadratic diophantine equation represented by

$$xy - (x + y) = \alpha \quad (\text{B-1})$$

where α is a Trimorphic number in turn.

Rewrite (B-1) as

$$x = \frac{\alpha + y}{y - 1} \quad (\text{B-2})$$

Given α , it is possible to find x in integers for suitable y in integers. The following Table:2 exhibits the Trimorphic number with their corresponding rectangles satisfying (B-1):

Table 2: $A - S = \alpha$

α	R(x,y)	Observation	
		Primitive rect-angles	Non-Primitive rectangles
24	(2, 26), (26, 2)	—	2
25	(2, 27), (3, 14), (14, 3), (27, 2)	4	—
49	(2, 51), (3, 26), (6, 11), (11, 6), (26, 3), (51, 2)	6	—
51	(2, 53), (3, 27), (5, 14), (14, 5), (27, 3), (53, 2)	4	2
75	(2, 77), (3, 39), (5, 20), (20, 5), (39, 3), (77, 2)	2	4
76	(2, 78), (8, 12), (12, 8), (78, 2)	—	4
99	(2, 101), (3, 51), (5, 26), (6, 21), (21, 6), (26, 5), (51, 3), (101, 2)	4	4
125	(2, 127), (3, 64), (4, 43), (8, 19), (10, 15), (15, 10), (19, 8), (43, 4), (64, 3), (127, 2)	8	2
249	(2, 251), (3, 126), (6, 51), (11, 26), (26, 11), (51, 6), (126, 3), (251, 2)	4	4
999	(2, 1001), (3, 501), (5, 251), (6, 201), (9, 126), (11, 101), (21, 51), (26, 41), (41, 26), (51, 21), (101, 11), (126, 9), (201, 6), (251, 5), (501, 3), (1001, 2)	8	8
1249	(2, 1251), (3, 626), (6, 251), (11, 126), (26, 51), (51, 26), (126, 11), (251, 6), (626, 3), (1251, 2)	10	—
3751	(2, 3753), (3, 1877), (5, 939), (8, 537), (9, 470), (15, 269), (29, 135), (57, 68), (68, 57), (135, 29), (269, 15), (470, 9), (537, 8), (939, 5), (1877, 3),	16	—

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Table 2 – *Continued from previous page*

α	R(x,y)	Observation	
		Primitive rectangles	Non-Primitive rectangles
	(3753, 2)		
4375	(2, 4377), (3, 2189), (5, 1095), (9, 548), (548, 9), (1095, 5), (2189, 3), (4377, 2)	6	2
4999	(2, 5001), (3, 2501), (5, 1251), (6, 1001), (9, 626), (11, 501), (21, 251), (26, 201), (41, 126), (51, 101), (101, 51), (126, 41), (201, 26), (251, 21), (501, 11), (626, 9), (1001, 6), (1251, 5), (2501, 3), (5001, 2)	20	–
5001	(2, 5003), (3, 2502), (42, 123), (62, 83), (83, 62), (123, 42), (2502, 3), (5003, 2)	4	4
9999	(2, 10001), (3, 5001), (5, 2501), (6, 2001), (9, 1251), (11, 1001), (17, 626), (21, 501), (26, 401), (41, 251), (51, 201), (81, 126), (126, 81), (201, 51), (251, 41), (401, 26), (501, 21), (626, 17), (1001, 11), (1251, 9), (2001, 6), (2501, 5), (5001, 3), (10001, 2)	10	14
18751	(2, 18753), (3, 9377), (5, 4689), (9, 2345), (17, 1173), (33, 587), (65, 294), (294, 65), (587, 33), (1173, 17), (2345, 9), (4689, 5), (9377, 3), (18753, 2)	12	2
31249	(2, 31251), (3, 15626), (6, 6251), (11, 3126), (26, 1251), (51, 626), (126, 251), (251, 126), (626, 51), (1251, 26), (3126, 11), (6251, 6), (15626, 3), (31251, 2)	14	–
49999	(2, 50001), (3, 25001), (5, 12501), (6, 10001), (9, 6251), (11, 5001), (17, 3126), (21, 2501), (26, 2001), (41, 1251), (51, 1001), (81, 626), (101, 501), (126, 401),	30	–

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Table 2 – Continued from previous page

α	R(x,y)	Observation	
		Primitive rect-angles	Non-Primitive rectangles
	(201, 251), (251, 201), (401, 126), (501, 101), (626, 81), (1001, 51), (1251, 41), (2001, 26), (2501, 21), (3126, 17), (5001, 11), (6251, 9), (10001, 6), (12501, 5), (25001, 3), (50001, 2)		
50001	(2, 50003), (3, 25002), (24, 2175), (47, 1088), (1088, 47), (2175, 24), (25002, 3), (50003, 2)	4	4

3. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we have presented rectangles such that, in each rectangle, the area added with its semi-perimeter as well as the area minus the semi-perimeter is represented by a Trimorphic number.

To conclude, one may search for rectangles with other characterization in connection with higher order Trimorphic numbers.

REFERENCES

- [1] W. Sierpinski. Pythagorean triangles, Dover publications, INC, Newyork, 2003.
- [2] M. A. Gopalan and A. Vijaysankar. Observations on a Pythagorean problem. Acta Ciencia Indica, Vol. XXXVI M, No.4,2010, p 517-520.
- [3] M. A. Gopalan, A. Gnanam and G. Janaki. A Remarkable Pythagorean problem, Acta Ciencia Indica, Vol. XXXIII M, No.4,2007, p 1429-1434.
- [4] M. A. Gopalan and A. Gnanam. Pythagorean triangles and Polygonal numbers. International Journal of Mathematical Sciences, Vol 9, No 1-2,2010, p 211-215,
- [5] M. A. Gopalan and G. Janaki. Pythagorean triangle with Area Perimeter as a special number. Bulletin of Pure and Applied sciences, 27(2),2008, p 393-402.
- [6] M. A. Gopalan and G. Janaki. Pythagorean triangle with nasty number as a leg, Journal of Applied Analysis and Applications, Vol 4, No 1-2,2008, p 13-17.
- [7] G. Janaki and R. Radha. Special Pythagorean triangle and six digit Harshad numbers. IJRSET, 5(3),March 2016, p 3931-3933,
- [8] G. Janaki and R. Radha. Special pairs of Pythagorean triangle and Harshad numbers. Asian Journal of Science and Technology, 7(8),August 2016, p 3397-3399.
- [9] G. Janaki and P. Saranya. Pythagorean Triangle with Area/Perimeter as a Jarasandha numbers of orders 2 and 4, IRJET, 3(7), July 2016, p 1259-1264.
- [10] G. Janaki and R. Radha. Pythagorean Triangle with Area/Perimeter as a Harshad number of digits 4,5 and 6. IJRASET, 5(12),December 2017, p 1754-1762,
- [11] G. Janaki and P. Saranya. Special Pythagorean triangle in connection with triangles Narcissistic Numbers of order 3 and 4. AIJRSTEM, 14(2),2016, p 150-153.
- [12] G. Janaki and P. Saranya. Special pairs of Pythagorean triangles and Narcissistic numbers, IJMRD, 3(4),April 2016, p 106-108.
- [13] S. Vidhyalakshmi, M. A. Gopalan and S. Aarth Thangam. A Connection between pairs of rectangles and Sphenic Numbers, JETIR, 6(1),January 2019,p 231-235.

- [14] Dr. A. Kavitha. A Connection between Pythagorean Triangle and Harshad Numbers, IJRASET, 7(3), March-2019, p 91-101.
- [15] S. Mallika. A Connection between Pythagorean Triangle and Sphenic Numbers. IJRASET, 7(3), March-2019, p 63-66,
- [16] M. A. Gopalan, J. Srilekha. Special Characterizations of Rectangles in Connection with Armstrong Numbers of order 3,4,5,6. IJMRAS, 2(3), March-2019, p 5-10,

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